

Technical and vocational education and training in sub-Saharan Africa: A comprehensive review of the current state of the research

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Introduction

Study commissioned by the *German Office for International Cooperation in Vocational Education and Training (GOVET)* in July 2018.

AIMS

- Undertake a systematic review of the state of research on TVET in SSA.
- Determine strategic directions for future TVET co-operation in SSA, with a focus on research and its operationalization.

RATIONALE

- VET plays a key role in the realization of SDGs.
- In SSA, there are only limited reliable results from TVET research
- The discourse and rationale on TVET are dominated by countries outside SSA - European and other Southeast Asia countries.

Research Questions

Research background

- Wider context of the research and institutional setting
- Specific academic disciplines
- Specific industrial sectors being researched
- Motivation of researchers
- TVET definition used (i.e., vocational training, apprenticeship etc.)
- TVET topics, perspectives and current debates addressed
- Regional trends and correlations

Research objectives and design

- Research goals
- Research questions pursued by researchers (issues or problems being tackled)
- Research design and methods used
- Research quality

Research findings and conclusions

- Research findings
- Recommendations for TVET provision, research or policy
- Impact of TVET programmes
- Relevant infrastructural, technological, socio-cultural, economic and legal enablers or challenges
- Inclusion enablers or challenges

Research questions (cont.)

TVET programmes being research

- Programme design or model
- Level of formality/informality
- Level of industry involvement

TVET state regulations

- Countries with national standards
- Countries with national inclusion standards
- TVET formality or informality (policy)
- National standards monitoring
- Regulation and assessment of TVET providers
- Evaluation of policy implementation
- Policy monitoring
- Impact of policy

TVET actors

- Designated experts in SSA
- Organisations researching TVET
- Research capacity
- Institutional framework/conditions
- Influence of framework/conditions on research performance
- Geographic distribution of most and least researched area
- National and international research networks
- Research funders
- Stakeholders in TVET policy and education system decision making
- TVET providers: private, NGOs, government, local or national

Methodology

Sequential design with a mixed methods approach:

- **Phase 1** - Systematic literature review through an online search. This included:
 - (a) Scientific literature: officially published in journals, conference papers, books, etc.
 - (b) "grey literature": unpublished project reports and project plans, working papers, policy papers, project reports, etc.
- **Phase 2** - Email-based survey consulting TVET stakeholders.
- **Phase 3** - Classification and grouping of retrieved literature, followed by coding, analysis and synthesis of documents graded as "High".
- **Phase 4** - Semi-structured interviews and focus groups to complement and complete the insights.
- **Phase 5** - Structured community review of the findings report.

Languages: search terms in English, French, Portuguese, German

FINDINGS: TVET research

Overview of the discovered literature

Thematic analysis - example

Program design, types of TVET, main features, practical program components, pedagogy (RQ7)		70%	212
Program design, types of TVET, key features (RQ7a)		57%	172
<i>Provision of TVET, TVET delivery and TVET systems (Including: Formality vs. Informality, RQ7c)</i>	<p>Mode of education provision (10%)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Informal apprenticeship (includes: formalization thereof) ● Informal sectoral conditions ● Regional differences: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Coastal West Africa: informal-formal ○ Sahel: informal-family Tanzania: informal-informal. <p>Dual system (2%)</p> <p>Justification, advantages and disadvantages, successes and failures of the “export of the dual system”, dual system experiments in different countries (Botswana, Ethiopia, Mali).</p> <p>Provision of TVET (2%)</p> <p>Distance learning (and international partnerships), company-based training and its impact on productivity, holistic models, flexible approaches.</p>	13%	39

Distribution of papers where research is focused

Who participates in TVET research?

Faculty or department	Number (all)	Number (SSA)
Education (including departments that focus specifically on technical education)	21	5
Health	27	16
Global health	2	0
Economics	3	1
Business or entrepreneurship	2	2
Engineering	9	4
Technology (including 'science and technology')	6	5
Miscellaneous	16	7
Other non-university and non-college entities	Number (all)	Number (SSA)
International organisations, research foundations and other non-university and non-college, not-for-profit institutions	16	10
TVET training institutions	1	1
National ministries, organisations and institutes	9	8

● Research gaps as motivation

- Firm-based training in the Global South region (Kweka, et al., 2006)
- Delivery of nursing training through an SMS-based approach (Duys, et al., 2017)
- Kenya's tourism industry (Mayaka, 2002).
- Training and development among middle-level managers in the Global South region (Abugre, & Adebola, 2015)
- Effects of entrepreneurship programmes in the Global South region (Garcia-Rodriguez, et al., 2017)
- A paucity of research **on China's role** in education and training in Africa was identified (King, 2010)
- Evaluation of the impact of technical training for artisans, particularly in rural areas (Ndegwa, 2015).
- Hospitality and tourism education beyond *"students' motivations and industry perceptions to the success of education"* (Tukamushaba, & Xiao, 2012).

● Potential for new technologies as motivation

● Societal changes as motivation

- e.g. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): Agriculture (SDG2); Nursing education and medical services (SDG3); Education (SDG4); Employability and entrepreneurship (SDG8); Marine environment (SDG14).

Who funds TVET research?

Funders appearing multiple times

- The Fogarty International Center
- DFID
- UNICEF

Funders appearing only once

- The African Development Bank (AfDB)
- **Europe:** The European Commission
- **UK:** The Cambridge Africa Partnership for Research Excellence – CAPREx
- **Germany:** GIZ
- **Switzerland:** The Swiss Development Corporation (SDC)
- **Japan:** The Japan International Cooperation Agency Research Institute (JICA RI), the Japan International Research Center for Agricultural Sciences (JIRCAS), and the Japan Society for the Promotion of Science (JSPS)
- **Canada:** The Canadian International Development Agency (CIDA), Plan International Canada and the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada

Research Networks

One global network that is easily identified is the **UNEVOC-Network** and its regional coordinating centres:

Central and Eastern Africa co-coordinating centre

Kenya's Department of Technology Education, University of Eldoret (UoEld).

Coordinating centre for Southern Africa co-coordinating centre

Botswana's Human Resource Development Council (HRDC).

Mozambique's National Directorate for Professional Technical Education (DINET).

West Africa co-coordinating centre

Nigeria's National Board for Technical Education (NBTE).

North Africa and Arab States co-coordinating centres

Egypt's Ministry of Education (MoE)

Morocco's College of Technical Education, Mohammed V Souissi University (UM5S).

FINDINGS: TVET provision

Overview of the discovered literature

Programmatic and pedagogical designs

The literature reveals that the programmatic designs employed in sub-Saharan Africa are:

1. Formalized college-based courses

Focusing on theoretical teaching, for example with 80% college-based learning and 20% non-college-based learning, although the literature has not established a fixed percentage split.

2. Formalized, dual-system approaches

Involving approximately 70% workplace-based activity and 30% of activity at a devoted learning center, following the proportions identified in Ethiopia.

3. Apprenticeship-only approaches

Which are almost entirely workplace-based, with limited learning center engagement);

4. Technology-supported distance learning (both initial and in-service)

5. In-service approaches and continuing professional development (CPD)

Pedagogical approaches

With regards to the key teaching approaches and classroom activities occurring within TVET programmes, the literature identified:

1. Regular emphasis on interactive pedagogy – Malawi, Cameroon, Tanzania, Uganda
2. Employment of non-interactive (lecture-focused) approaches, that occasionally centred on lectures from foreign guests - Tanzania, Ghana, South Africa
3. An interest in the employment of ICT for teaching and learning - Kenya, Rwanda, Benin

Informal TVET in Africa and regions

Western vs. Southern and Eastern Africa

There seems to be a consensus in the literature regarding the differences between the informal TVET system in Western versus in Southern and Eastern Africa. Apprenticeships in Western Africa is considered to be much more structured than in Southern and Eastern African countries.

Urban vs. rural

Regarding the location, apprenticeships are most available in urban areas than in rural.

Inclusion-related challenges and policies

- Disability
- Gender
 - Women's access to education
 - Women in TVET
 - Women's employment and the labour market
 - Gender-based roles, career choices and gender stereotypes
 - Gender and teacher education
- Other vulnerable groups, based on:
 - economic status
 - geographical location
 - age (e.g. youth)
 - ethnic origin (e.g. refugees)
 - religion

FINDINGS: TVET policies

Overview of the discovered literature

Government sector mapping

- In the majority of countries in SSA the **Ministry of Education** and/or the **Ministry of Labour** are the most important state authorities in decision making and management of the TVET system at the national level.
- The role of other players - we found very little references to other institutions involved in TVET
- In some countries, the industrial or commercial sectors are formally involved in the TVET system as training providers, as an advisory committee, and through participation in the development of policies or training curriculum.
- While there was some research on policy, there is no evidence for the influence of research findings on TVET policy, neither at the national or regional level.

National Standards and Qualifications Framework

Country and Year of Publication	Qualifications Framework/National Standards	Published or established by
Botswana, 1997	NPVET - National Policy on Vocational Education and Training	MLHA - Ministry of Labour and Home Affairs
Botswana, 2005	BNVQF - Botswana National Vocational Qualifications Framework	BOTA - Botswana Training Authority
Botswana, 2016	NCQF - National Credit and Qualifications Framework	BQA - Botswana Qualification Authority
Ghana	NTVETQF - National Technical and Vocational Education and Training Qualifications Framework	COTVET - Council for Technical and Vocational Education and Training
Kenya, 2014	KNQF Act - Kenya National Qualifications Framework Act N° 22	National Council of Law
Kenya, 2015	National Industrial Training Standards	NITA - National Industrial Training Authority
Kenya, 2018	CBETA Standards and Guidelines - TVETA Competency Based Education and Training and Assessment Standards & Guidelines	TVETA - Technical and Vocational Education and Training Authority
Malawi, 2015	National Education Standards - primary and secondary education	MoEST - Ministry of Education, Science and Technology
Mauritius, 2001	MQA Act - Mauritius Qualifications Authority Act No. 42	Federal Government

TVET specific qualification frameworks and sector strategic plans

We found specific TVET qualification frameworks in three countries:

- Botswana
- Ghana
- Uganda

Web search also encountered strategic plans designed specifically for the TVET sector in the following countries:

- Botswana - ETSSP 2015-2020 - Education & Training Sector Strategic Plan
- Kenya - TVET Strategic Plan 2018-2022
- Uganda - BTVET Strategic Plan 2011-2020
- South Africa - Human Resource Development Strategy for South Africa 2010-2030.

Monitoring of TVET standards

Country	State Authority	Functions and responsibilities.
Botswana	BOTA	Definition and regulation of national TVET standards Collection of information from training providers Definition of TVET regulations Advisor for the Minister on TVET matters
	BQA	Monitoring and evaluation of TVET quality assurance standards Advisor for the Minister on quality standards matters
Ghana	TVED	Monitors and evaluation of public Technical Training Institutes and private TVET providers TVET examinations and certifications
	COTVET	Formulates national policies for skills development
Kenya	TVETA	Registration, licensing, and accreditation of institutions, programmes and trainers Management of the TVET National Quality Assurance System Determination of National TVET objectives Advice government in all matters training
	NITA	Inspection of industrial training providers
	TVET CDACC	Design and develop CBET curricula and carry out competence assessment and certification.

Regulation of TVET providers

Country	Year of Publication	State TVET regulations
Ghana	2007	Polytechnic Law
Kenya	2016	Guidelines for Registration of Training Providers TVET act 2013 and the regulations of 2015 (www.tveta.go.ke)
Mauritius	2009	Mauritius Qualifications Authority regulations
Nigeria	1985	Education (National Minimum Standards and Establishment of Institutions) Act N° 16
	1987	Educational Correspondence Colleges Accreditation Act N° 32
	2014	Guidelines and Procedures for the Establishment of Private Technical and Technological Institutions
	2006	Guidelines for Establishment and Operation of Production Unit in Technical College
	2007	Standards and Criteria for Approval of Programmes in Vocational Enterprise Institutions (VEI) & Innovation Enterprise Institutions Programmes (IEI)
South Africa	2015	National Policy on Community Education and Training Colleges
	2011	Integrated strategic planning framework for teacher education and development in South Africa, 2011-2025
Uganda	2013	Guidelines for licensing and regulating of private schools after SPM

Building TVET Research Capacity

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